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SDGs-related research and scientists' relational involvement with non-academic actors

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Introduction and Background

The United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are aimed to tackle the grand challenges of our era. Global problems that are difficult to face at a country level, such as environmental degradation or socio-economic inequality, have now a common framework of action since 2015, when 193 countries agreed the 2030 Agenda (United Nations, 2015). Although this collective plan has not been free of criticism mainly by ecological economists and critical political scientists (Brissett & Mitter, 2017; Heleta & Bagus, 2021; Swain, 2018), it has been extensively agreed by many relevant actors, including businesses, governments, and universities, among others. The SDGs have been the result of a great effort of participation and consultation to formulate policies at both national and local levels towards sustainability. This effort was materialised in September 2015 in 17 main objectives to be reach by 2030, subdivided into 169 sub-objectives (United Nations, 2015, 2021), which can also be grouped into 5 key areas (people, planet, prosperity, peace and partnerships) coping with the economic, social and environmental sustainability.

The societal goals embodied in the SDGs have critical implications for the public university system and the role played by academic scientists. Specifically, they boost the transition from traditional university research and knowledge to a mission-driven demand for knowledge and solutions. This perspective has been already underlined by several related conceptual frameworks: the triple helix model (Leydesdorff & Etzkowitz, 1996), mode 1 and mode 2 of knowledge production (Gibbons et al., 1994), the entrepreneurial university (Clark, 1998), and more recently, the mission-oriented innovation model (Mazzucato, 2018). Furthermore, the outside-in approach to universities to address the SDGs stimulates interdisciplinary solutions (Rafols et al., 2021) or even transdisciplinary research (Marques, 2019), which brings practitioners as active participants into the projects (Schaltegger et al., 2013). Consequently, universities are increasingly pushed to reach a new balance among its three primary missions (namely, teaching, research, and knowledge transfer). Thus, for universities, this governance challenge implies a closer cooperation not only with their internal stakeholders (e.g.: faculty members, administrative staff, and students), but also with their external ones.

Against this background, most of the existing research exploring the influence of the SDGs on the university system has constrained their analyses to the macro-level (e.g.: regional or institutional). Our study adopts an individual-level approach to explore the extent to which the

SDGs discourse and initiatives have influenced university scientists' practices. Specifically, we address scientist' research alignment with SDGs (hereafter, SDGs-related research) and its association with scientist' relational involvement with non-academics (hereafter, relational involvement). Relational involvement is a form of interaction between scientists and non-academic actors that necessarily requires direct participation of the parties, which is not necessarily true for commercialization activities such as patent licensing or academic spin-off (Perkmann & Walsh, 2007). Hence, it encompasses activities characterised by interpersonal interactions between academic and non-academic partners (Schartinger et al., 2006). For instance, academics' participation in consulting, collaborative research, ad-hoc advice or personnel mobility would qualify in this category (e.g.: D'Este and Patel, 2007; Perkmann and Walsh, 2009; Hughes et al., 2016).

The aim of this paper is twofold. The first objective is to explore the extent to which the SDG challenges are actually ingrained in academics' research agendas. The second objective is to disentangle the relationship between SDGs-related research and relational involvement. To achieve these objectives, we conduct a literature review and derive the following hypotheses that are empirically tested.

Hypothesis 1: Scientists with high levels of SDG-inspired research will exhibit greater relational involvement with non-academics, as compared to scientists with low levels of SDG-inspired research.

Hypothesis 2: Scientists with high levels of SDG-inspired research will exhibit greater engagement in personnel mobility, as compared to research services.

Overall, the paper offers two main contributions. First, we identify groups (clusters) of scientists based on the extent to which their research is related to SDGs and characterise them in terms of diverse personal and professional attributes. Second, we explore whether scientists whose research is more aligned with SDGs tend to interact more with non-academic actors, distinguishing between different forms of relational involvement.

Methods

Population and data collection

This empirical study is part of broader research project funded by the Valencian Regional Government, which aims at exploring researchers' willingness to incorporate external non-academic influences in their research processes. The population for this study consisted of faculty members with research duties, of four Spanish public universities affiliated to the departments of arts, social sciences, humanities (SSH), in the Valencian Region. This population was chosen to ensure, as much as possible, homogeneous conditions for all the participants as higher education competences in Spain are transferred to regional governments. Moreover, we put the focus on the field of SSH because it has been traditionally understudied in the literature on university-industry interactions (Perkmann et al., 2021), despite being a field with potential to provide critical inputs to address societal grand challenges (Spaapen & Sivertsen, 2020), such as the SDGs.

Data was gathered through a survey directly addressed to all faculty members affiliated to SSH departments from all four universities. The population was identified through the institutional information publicly available in universities' websites. The survey was developed from a literature review on the production of societally relevant research and academic engagement

(Abreu & Grinevich, 2017; D’Este et al., 2017; Olmos-Peñuela et al., 2015; Perkmann et al., 2013). Data was gathered between December 2019 and March 2020. We ended up with a final sample of 614 faculty members. The response rate was 20.7%, being representative of the population of study in terms of university affiliation, field and sex.

Measures

To capture scientist’ relational involvement with non-academic actors, respondents were asked to evaluate their degree of involvement in different forms of academic engagement activities during the last 3 years. Relational involvement were identified through different activities, including research services (e.g.: consulting activities or contract research), or personal-based activities (e.g.: temporary visits to non-academic institutions). For all the activities, responses could range from 0 (“Never”) to 4 (“At least once a month”). We performed a factor analysis to reduce the broad set of activities into a smaller number of latent factors. We employed principal component method to estimate the factors, and an orthogonal varimax rotation to extract them for better interpretability (Field, 2018). Two factors were extracted. From a conceptual standpoint, the two extracted factors correspond to relational activities that are clearly interpretable. Factor 1 (“research services”) depicts a set of academic engagement practices in which scientists have ready-to-sell codified knowledge (D’Este et al., 2019; Perkmann & Walsh, 2007); this includes activities such as contract research or academic consulting. Factor 2 (“personnel mobility”) represents situations where individuals move between academic and non-academic institutions, such as scientists’ research stays in non-academic institutions or practitioners’ hosting in academic institutions.

To measure scientists’ SGD-related research, we asked them to report their degree of agreement (from 1 ‘strongly disagree’ to 7 ‘strongly agree’) regarding whether their research relates to five different SDG categories, namely prosperity, people, peace, planet and partnership. We thus obtained five variables that captured the extent to which their research is aligned to each of the five SDGs categories. These five variables were used in a subsequent cluster analysis, which resulted into two types of researchers: those conducting high SDG-related research (high-SDG) and those conducting low SDG-related research (low-SDG). We employed this dummy variable in our regression models.

We also considered a set of control variables to account for alternative personal and professional characteristics of scientists that, according to the literature, might influence their degree of relational involvement, such as the hierarchical position; university to which they belong, department field, gender, year since PhD, experience inside and outside academia and the time distribution across academic activities (teaching, research, knowledge transfer and management).

Analysis and preliminary findings

Cluster analysis

We performed a cluster analysis to obtain a typology of scientists according to the extent to which their research was inspired by the SGDs. We used a two-stage procedure approach. First, we run a hierarchical agglomerative procedure based on the Ward’s method using squared Euclidean distances. We used the clusters centroids obtained from this first hierarchical procedure as initial seeds to run a non-hierarchical analysis with k-means (Steinley, 2006). We obtained a two-cluster solution, which showed that cluster 1 was formed by faculty members that reported low SDG-related research (C1, n=338) and a second cluster with faculty members that reported high SDG-related research (C2, n=276).

Then, we assessed whether there were differences across clusters for each of the defining (SDG-related research) and associated (personal and professional attributes) variables by means of t-test analysis for continuous variables and Chi-Square statistic for categorical variables. Differences across clusters were found in all the defining variables, but also in some associated variables such as department field, hierarchical position, Stokes quadrants and public administration experience. Conversely, results indicate that the descriptive statistics for the clusters according to university, gender, academic experience, firm experience; years since the PhD, and time devoted to teaching and management duties do not show significant differences.

Regression models

We assessed the relationship between SDG-related research and relational involvement (“research services” and “personnel mobility”) by means of regressions. Our two dependent variables share two important characteristics. First, both variables are restricted in range, as they can only take values between 0 (‘never’) to 4 (‘at least once a month’). Second, although our two dependent variables are conceptually distinct, they are unlikely to be fully independent events. It might be that unobserved factors are influencing both dependent variables. Therefore, to explicitly take account of the censoring and interdependence of the two dependent variables, we employed a bivariate Tobit regression (Blundell & Meghir, 1987; Rogge & Schleich, 2018).

Overall, the regression results show that the coefficient associated to the variable high-SDG has a positive and statistically significant relationship with “research services” and “personnel mobility”. Thus, scientists whose research is highly aligned with the SDGs exhibit greater levels of relational involvement. Moreover, we conducted a Wald test and found that the difference between both coefficients were significantly different from zero, which indicates that the positive relationship between SDG-related research and relational involvement is stronger for personnel mobility, as compared to research services.

Conclusions and implications

This study aims first at exploring to what extent the alignment of SSH scientists’ research to the SDGs differs from those scientists whose research is not (or little) related to the SDGs. Given the importance of the challenges that SDGs pose to all 193 countries that agree in 2015 to support them, our study opens up an interesting research avenue. Despite not having any explicit incentive to do so, a large part of our sample of scientists have aligned their research agenda towards the SDGs. Moreover, two patterns of scientists have been identified, according to their level of engagement with the SDGs. Interestingly, our results suggest that a greater research alignment with SDGs implies a more active engagement with non-academic actors. Specifically, scientists whose research is SDG-related seems to participate more actively in relational involvement activities, namely, personnel mobility and research services. This has important implications for university policies; therefore, should universities aim at promoting societally relevant research and its uptake by societal actors, more coordinating efforts will be needed to strengthen the current top-down approach and its effect on scientists’ academic practices.

References

- Abreu, M., & Grinevich, V. (2017). Gender patterns in academic entrepreneurship. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 42(4), 763–794.
- Blundell, R., & Meghir, C. (1987). Bivariate alternatives to the Tobit model. *Journal of Econometrics*, 34(1), 179–200.
- Brissett, N., & Mitter, R. (2017). For function or transformation? A critical discourse analysis of education under the Sustainable Development Goals. *Journal for Critical Education Policy Studies (JCEPS)*, 15(1).
- Clark, B. R. (1998). *Creating Entrepreneurial Universities: Organizational Pathways of Transformation*. Emerald Publishing Limited.
- D’Este, P., Llopis, O., Rentocchini, F., & Yegros, A. (2019). The relationship between interdisciplinarity and distinct modes of university-industry interaction. *Research Policy*, 48(9), 103799.
- D’Este, P., Llopis, O., & Yegros, A. (2017). Conducting pro-social research: Exploring the behavioral antecedents to knowledge transfer among scientists. In *The World Scientific Reference on Entrepreneurship* (Vol. 4, pp. 19–54).
- D’Este, P., & Patel, P. (2007). University–industry linkages in the UK: What are the factors underlying the variety of interactions with industry? *Research Policy*, 36(9), 1295–1313. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2007.05.002>
- Field, A. (2018). *Discovering statistics using IBM SPSS statistics*. Sage.
- Gibbons, M., Limoges, C., Nowotny, H., Schwartzman, S., Scott, P., & Trow, M. (1994). *The New Production of Knowledge: The Dynamics of Science and Research in Contemporary Societies*. SAGE Publications.
- Heleta, S., & Bagus, T. (2021). Sustainable development goals and higher education: Leaving many behind. *Higher Education*, 81(1), 163–177.
- Leydesdorff, L., & Etzkowitz, H. (1996). Emergence of a Triple Helix of university—industry—government relations. *Science and public policy*, 23(5), 279–286.
- Marques, J. (2019). Creativity and morality in business education: Toward a trans-disciplinary approach. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 17(1), 15–25.
- Mazzucato, M. (2018). Mission-oriented innovation policies: Challenges and opportunities. *Industrial and Corporate Change*, 27(5), 803–815.
- Olmos-Peñuela, J., Benneworth, P., & Castro-Martínez, E. (2015). What Stimulates Researchers to Make Their Research Usable? Towards an ‘Openness’ Approach. *Minerva*, 53(4), 381–410.
- Perkmann, M., Salandra, R., Tartari, V., McKelvey, M., & Hughes, A. (2021). Academic engagement: A review of the literature 2011–2019. *Research Policy*, 50(1), 104114.

Perkmann, M., Tartari, V., McKelvey, M., Autio, E., Broström, A., D'Este, P., Fini, R., Geuna, A., Grimaldi, R., Hughes, A., Krabel, S., Kitson, M., Llerena, P., Lissoni, F., Salter, A., & Sobrero, M. (2013). Academic engagement and commercialisation: A review of the literature on university–industry relations. *Research Policy*, 42(2), 423–442.

Perkmann, M., & Walsh, K. (2007). University–industry relationships and open innovation: Towards a research agenda. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 9(4), 259–280.

Perkmann, M., & Walsh, K. (2009). The two faces of collaboration: Impacts of university–industry relations on public research. *Industrial and Corporate Change*, 18(6), 1033–1065.

Rafols, I., Noyons, E., Confraria, H., & Ciarli, T. (2021). *Visualising plural mappings of science for Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)* [Preprint]. SocArXiv.

Rogge, K. S., & Schleich, J. (2018). Do policy mix characteristics matter for low-carbon innovation? A survey-based exploration of renewable power generation technologies in Germany. *Research Policy*, 47(9), 1639–1654.

Schaltegger, S., Beckmann, M., & Hansen, E. G. (2013). Transdisciplinarity in Corporate Sustainability: Mapping the Field. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 22(4), 219–229.

Schartinger, D., Rammer, C., & Fröhlich, J. (2006). Knowledge interactions between universities and industry in Austria: Sectoral patterns and determinants. In *Innovation, networks, and knowledge spillovers* (pp. 135–166). Springer.

Spaapen, J., & Sivertsen, G. (2020). Assessing societal impact of SSH in an engaging world: Focus on productive interaction, creative pathways and enhanced visibility of SSH research. *Research Evaluation*, 29(1), 1–3.

Steinley, Douglas. (2006). K-means clustering: A half-century synthesis. *British Journal of Mathematical and Statistical Psychology*, 59(1), 1–34.

Swain, R. B. (2018). A Critical Analysis of the Sustainable Development Goals. In W. Leal Filho (Ed.), *Handbook of Sustainability Science and Research* (pp. 341–355). Springer International Publishing.

United Nations. (2015). *Transforming our world: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development* | Department of Economic and Social Affairs. <https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>

United Nations (2021). 17 Goals to Transform Our World. Available at: <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/sdgs> (accessed 11 June 2021).

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